

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATION APPROACH

Yakubova Feruza Yusufovna

Researcher at Tashkent state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7684131>

Abstract. *The educational environment can be viewed as a sum/set of historically formed/developed factors, circumstances, situations and specially organized pedagogical conditions for the development of a student's personality.*

Keywords: *analysis, education, student, system, development.*

The analysis of the sources is that the innovative educational environment of training qualified bachelors is a continuous multi-level system that works in the conditions of continuous education, multivariate, independent development, expansion of the educational space, development and implementation of a multi-component change model reflecting the integration, acmeological conditions and factors of the formation process, characteristics of the socio-cultural environment of the subjects' life and the development and implementation of a model reflecting the result-oriented preparation of a competent, competitive specialist can be reached to the conclusion allows [13].

It is self-evident that the main directions of optimization of the formation of HE educational environment can be the following: emphasis on the formation of key competences included in the invariants of professionalism; use of strategies and tactics, as well as diagnostics/diagnostics of level formation; based on the potential advantages of technologies aimed at optimizing the organizational-methodical, content and professional components of the process of forming an educational environment for training specialists and overcoming the disadvantages of implementing a multi-level system of OCT. Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of the characteristics of two models of educational institutions of two different types.

Analyzing the differences in resource availability of traditional and innovative types of educational institutions, it is not difficult to see that, in the first instance, efficiency ensures equal availability of all types of resources.

In the second case, the main source of efficiency is personnel/employees, because the size/number/amount of invested human capital primarily depends on:

- innovative potential of personnel;
- Organization of management of innovative processes in HEIs;
- organization of the information environment and the level of information technology mastery of employees.

Table 5.

Comparative analysis of traditional and innovative educational institutions

	A traditional type of educational institution	Innovative educational institution

1. Work with information resources	Mastering the volume of educational and scientific resources necessary for teaching specific knowledge, skills and abilities.	Master the technologies of continuous search for new information in the environment of large amount of information resources of unknown size
2. Educational technologies	The set/list of technologies is defined according to the given methodology.	In the process of teaching, technologies are constantly updated and new ones are developed
3. Material and technical base	Unchanged throughout the study	It will be developed according to technological re-equipment
4. Costs of education	Externally determined according to the given technologies and material and technical support.	Compare prices for educational services

Thus, the educational environment can be viewed as a sum/set of historically formed/developed factors, circumstances, situations and specially organized pedagogical conditions for the development of a student's personality. In a broad sense, the social-cultural educational environment can be understood as a structure that includes several interrelated levels. Global trends in the development of culture, economy, politics and education can be included at the global level. At the regional level (countries, large regions) - educational policy, culture, educational system. The local level can include the educational institution and the family. The local educational environment can be considered as a system that includes microculture, communication, educational content, personality of the pedagogue, teaching and upbringing methodology and many other things. During his life, a person goes through many educational environments. A learning environment is a system that, despite its organization/coherence, is not static. He experiences all the changes in society and culture, and in a natural way, and he himself also affects them at the same time. There is a conservative educational environment, such as religion, that changes dynamically, but the most static system is inevitably subject to change. When they collide with each other, environments are deformed (change their shape), and this leads to transformation (change) and, as a result, the development of the educational environment.

The analysis of the development characteristics of the modern education system allowed to identify the vectors of educational environment strategies that implement the first level of higher professional education. Among the main vectors, we can mention the following:

- training of a competent specialist who meets the requirements of scientific-technical and socio-economic development of society and personal interests in the conditions of international quality standards;
- formation of the student's professional and cultural competence, readiness to carry out professional activities in the conditions of development of production and social relations;
- development of innovative processes, use of new technologies and training tools that ensure the formation of the personality of a specialist capable of determining and developing his/her own professional fate/future.

The level of professional-pedagogical preparation of the teacher can be considered as one of the important conditions for the formation of general cultural competences of students

in the innovative educational environment. The professional-pedagogical competence of the teacher refers to pedagogical experience and pedagogical culture, mastery of new innovative pedagogical, information and industrial technologies. level is understood. As the components of professional-pedagogical competence, we consider special competences, knowledge in the field of the taught subject, pedagogical and methodical competences - in the field of technologies for the formation of general cultural competence of students, social-psychological competences - in the field of communication processes, differential-psychological competences, incentives/motives for the formation of professional-cultural competence of students and field of orientation; professional - we can distinguish according to the profile of the specialty that the student receives. The professional-pedagogical competence of the teacher implies the formation of design, constructive and communicative skills at a high level in the use of theoretical-methodical, theoretical, methodical, technological knowledge and the ability to effectively apply scientific professional-pedagogical knowledge in practice. The indicator of the teacher's professional-pedagogical competence is the ability to predict the development of the general cultural competence of the student, because the results of the pedagogical influence and cross-activity are significantly delayed. The high professional-pedagogical level of the teacher, based on scientific and industry knowledge, skillfully implemented by the system of methods and technologies, ensures a high level of general cultural competence of the student.

The next condition for the formation of general cultural competence of students is the creation of an educational-informational environment, which includes the educational-material/material and educational-program base of higher education institutions, which contributes to the dynamic development of information competence of students and increases the level of saturation with science, intellectualization and virtualization of the work of future specialists. training of informationally/informationally competent personnel. The integrity of the information-educational environment is ensured by the continuity and interaction of the used teaching technologies, the comparison of the information-educational environment with the factors that form the general cultural competence of students, the combination/comparison of technical and humanitarian education elements based on the selection of the criteria of general cultural competence. The multidimensional information-educational environment of the educational institution - forms the information culture and competence of teachers and students, creates a potential opportunity for students to effectively adapt to the demands of the labor market, society and themselves. Creating an information-educational environment activates the creative abilities of teachers and students: electronic courses and textbooks are created, the level of professional qualification/skills of teachers and the reputation of the educational institution among employers and the public increases. The increase in scientific saturation, intellectualization and virtualization of the future specialist's work is a positive result of the activity of the created information-educational environment.

Factors related to students' personal characteristics (level and quality of motivation/motivation, basic level of formation of components of students' general cultural competence, independent self-regulation/regulation, communication skills) are also included in the conditions that contribute to the development of general cultural competence of students. From a methodological point of view, the whole cycle of humanitarian sciences should be supported by the psychological service of the Higher Education Institution in order to optimize

the educational process and regulate the educational climate taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of students. During the entire period of teaching/studying at the HEI, there are crisis stages where almost all students face similar psychological problems: the stage of adaptation/adjustment to studying/studying at the selected HEI; the stage of formation of professional identity/identity - "crisis of the 2nd-3rd year"; the stage of determining one's professional future/destiny and job search for a specialty (4th year), and the individual-psychological characteristics of students have a significant impact on solving these problems. At these crisis stages, psychological-pedagogical support of students (and essentially - psychological-pedagogical provision/support of the entire educational process in HEIs), correction of personal characteristics of character and behavior, methods of communication, not only prevent possible negative aspects from appearing, but allows the development of individual-psychological characteristics of students, and these characteristics are components of a number of general cultural competences (Table 6).

Correspondence of individual-psychological characteristics of students with general cultural competences

Individual-psychological characteristics of students	Competencies
The formation of value goals/orientations (the student supports professional values)	Knowledge of legal and moral/ethical norms, their application in professional activity
High educational motivation (motivation to acquire knowledge and to acquire a profession)	The ability to critically review the accumulated experience, if necessary, to change the profile of one's professional activity; The ability to constantly improve and deepen knowledge, initiative and leadership
The formation of cognitive independence (the student can plan independent work and devote serious time to it)	The ability to improve one's knowledge and constant readiness for this, the ability to quickly adapt to any situation; Ability to edit and organize own work and team work
The formation of interpersonal relationships (the student can establish relationships with classmates and teachers)	Working independently and in a team, working with and leading people, and subordinating personal interests to a common goal
Emotional well-being (absence of a background of constant high level of personal anxiety)	The basis for effective formation of all competencies

The idea of developing personal qualities/virtues in students, on the one hand, which will allow them to successfully study/study in the chosen specialty/specialty, and on the other hand, which will form the psychological basis of general cultural competencies of the future specialist, is one of the signs of the innovative educational environment. It can be implemented in the program of psychological-pedagogical support during the period of adaptation and during the entire education. In the content of the psychological service program: at the beginning of the academic year, psycho-diagnostic/diagnostic measures can be included, which allow to identify "risk groups", that is, students with an unfavorable prognosis of socio-

psychological adaptation to study.

At the same time, business games and psychological games aimed at teaching first-year students to properly organize their educational activities, preparing for exams, increasing motivation/motivation to study, teaching self-regulation/regulation skills, developing communication skills, and improving the microclimate in study groups. It is necessary to develop a training system. In this case, the joint efforts of the higher educational institution administration, teaching staff and psychological service to form personal qualities/qualities for understanding and acceptance of general cultural competences, help students to overcome the crisis of professional choice, determine their own future in their profession and find a job in their specialty necessary, that is: development of educational and research activities of students, including the programs of ITIs based on the contract; introduction of problem-based education as one of the non-standard methods of training, introduction of personal (named) scholarships, introduction of awards for educational and research works; Employment of the most successful students after graduation from higher education institutions; career orientation and interpersonal communication, personal and professional growth training, individual psychological counseling, effective job placement processes and modeling of business games; creating a student labor exchange, etc. will be necessary.

It is clear that today a high school teacher cannot be just a transmitter of knowledge. The personality of the teacher, his value system - professional, general cultural and pedagogical competences are the basis for the formation of general cultural competences of students. For this reason, the composition of personnel (employees) of HEIs, that is, the personal and professional characteristics of the teaching staff (the level of personal and information culture, readiness to accept innovations, encouragement/motivation to improve professional and pedagogical skills), as well as the interaction between pedagogues and students features are one of the important conditions of the innovative educational environment, which contribute to the formation of universal competences.

In the framework/context of our research, striving for continuous improvement of theoretical training (teaching) of teachers, acquisition of diagnosis/diagnosis, research, analytical activity skills, work on creating educational programs and teaching-methodical materials, etc. The factor of attitude to quality innovations is of serious importance. The main characteristics of teachers' tendency to innovative activity are:

- modernity - constant pursuit of didactic innovations and continuous improvement of teaching content, taking into account scientific and technical achievements, changes taking place in society;
- optimality - high-quality professional, personal and general cultural competence, efficiency and positive results of students in return for achieving the set goals, spending the least amount of time and effort;
- integration - creating a system of acquiring knowledge related to the achievements of the system of general cultural, general humanitarian and special sciences based on the achievements of psychological-pedagogical sciences and teaching methodology;
- scientificity-transition to determining the content of educational methods and forms based on the latest achievements of psychological and pedagogical science and fundamental sciences;
- designing individual development trajectories of students; extensive use of modern

teaching tools and methods that activate students' professional-educational activities. Thus, the innovative educational environment of HEIs is a multi-dimensional socio-cultural and pedagogical phenomenon/phenomenon, specially organized in HEIs, which includes professional activities of teachers and students in all the diversity of their relationships with the surrounding world. development of all educational subjects and self-development, the formation of professional, including general cultural competence of future specialists, the development of their personal and professional goals/directions, –is a multi-factor influencing space that activates incentives/motives and personal tendencies in the development of the professional education program and further professional activities. Wide integration of higher education students into the educational process through the use of interactive educational forms is one of the conditions for the formation of universal competence in an innovative educational environment. In this regard, the nature and functions of vocational education are changing today: it is not only the transfer of knowledge and the development of skills, but also the development of the ability to determine one's own destiny / future, preparing future professionals for independent actions / actions and their responsibility for themselves and their actions / actions. should be taught to take responsibility. The nature of the interaction between the teacher and the students also changes in quality. The student becomes not the object of education, but the subject of this process, and the pedagogue becomes its (process) organizer. This leads to the need to consider the meaningful processes of interaction in the educational system. Such processes are based on formation of a high psychological culture of the teacher, development of his ability to communicate with students, creation of an open educational space that ensures the creative growth of each student.

The teacher's ability to reveal the student's internal resources using interactive forms in teaching can provide constructive changes in the learning process, help a young person to assess his abilities and opportunities, correctly determine his place in life and open the way for him to realize a fulfilling professional career. [46, 12 p.]. We believe that the attempt to "introduce" the competency-based approach based on the reproductive methods of teaching and training will fail, because competencies can be formed in an innovative educational environment only as a result of the student's involvement in the educational process, which is based on active and interactive forms of training (dialogue, computer modeling and practical analysis of the results, seminars in the mode of scientific discussions, work of student research groups, videoconferences of HEIs and inter-HEIs, etc.) defines a wide use in combination with extracurricular activities in order to form and develop the professional and personal character/qualities of students.

Meetings with representatives of Uzbek and foreign companies, state and public organizations, sample/skill classes (master classes) by experts and specialists should be part of the training courses. The average contribution of classes conducted in active and interactive forms is determined by the purpose of the curriculum, the characteristics of the student body/contingent, and the content of certain/concrete subjects. In this –context, the content of the training program becomes a means of developing personality components of professional competence. Today, the curriculum regulates the number of hours allocated to lessons using interactive teaching methods. Educational-methodological complex/complexes of sciences reflect the whole spectrum of interactive forms of teaching. However, the problem of increasing the efficiency of their use in the educational process is still relevant.

We consider interactive educational technologies as ways of acquiring knowledge, forming skills and abilities in the process of interaction and interaction between the pedagogue and the student as subjects of educational activity. Their essence is that they rely not only on the processes of perception, memory and attention, but also, above all, on creative and productive thinking, behavior and communication. In this, the educational process in the innovative educational environment is organized in such a way that students learn to communicate, learn to interact with each other and other people, learn critical thinking, solve complex problems based on the analysis of pedagogical situations, situational professional tasks and relevant information. In interactive educational technologies, the role of the teacher (instead of the role of the informant/informer, the role of manager/leader) and the learners (instead of the object of influence, the subject of cross-activity), as well as the role of information (information is not a goal, but a means of mastering actions/works and operations) change significantly. All interactive educational technologies are divided into non-simulated and simulated types. Classification is based on the sign of restoration (imitation) of the context of professional pedagogical activity, its presentation/expression as a model in education. Non-imitation technologies do not involve building models of the studied phenomenon or activity. The basis of imitation (imitation) technologies is imitation or imitation-game modeling, that is, re-development/repetition of processes occurring in the real system with one or another degree of relevance/compatibility/adequacy in educational conditions.

The effectiveness of using interactive forms of education in the innovative educational environment is ensured by the implementation of the following pedagogical conditions: creating a dialogic space in the organization of the educational process; use of socio-psychological principles of transition in educational and extracurricular activities; control of personal characteristics and professional orientation of students; formation of psychological readiness of teachers to use interactive forms aimed at developing students' internal activity of teaching.

Let's consider some technologies of interactive teaching/learning in the innovative environment of HEI. "Problem speech" implies setting a problem, a problematic situation and solving them later. In the problem lecture, the conflicts of real life are modeled by expressing them in theoretical concepts. The main purpose of such a lecture is to gain knowledge with direct and positive result/effective participation of students. Modeled problems may include scientific, social, and professional problems related to the specific content of the educational material. Setting (giving) a problem encourages students to think actively, to try to answer the question independently, arouses interest in the presented material and activates students' attention.

"Debat" (seminar-dimput) implies a collective discussion of a problem in order to determine reliable ways to solve it. The debate-seminar is held in the form of a dialog between its participants. It requires high mental activity, inculcates/trains the skills of holding a debate, discussing a problem, defending your views and beliefs, expressing your thoughts concisely and clearly. The roles of practitioners in the debate-seminar may be different.

"Learning discussion/discussion" is one of the problem-based teaching/learning methods. It is used in the analysis of problematic situations when it is necessary to give a simple and unambiguous answer to the question, and it is assumed that there are alternative answers. In order to involve all those who participated in the discussion, it is advisable to use the method of cooperative teaching (educational cooperation). This methodology is based on mutual teaching/learning with students working together in small groups. The basic idea of educational

cooperation is very simple: students combine their intellectual efforts to perform a common task or achieve a common goal (for example, to find a solution to a problem). The working technology of the study group in educational/educational cooperation can be as follows:

- pose a problem.
- formation of small groups (microgroups of 5-7 people), distribution of roles in them, explanation of the expected participation in the discussion by the teacher;
- discuss the problem in microgroups;
- giving/presenting the results of the discussion to the whole study group;
- continue the discussion and summarize/conclude the results. "Brainstorming" aims to collect as many ideas as possible, to free students from thinking inertia, to activate creative thinking, to overcome the usual flow of thoughts in problem solving. "Brainstorming" makes it possible to significantly increase the efficiency of creating new ideas in the study group. The main principles and rules of this method are absolutely to criticize the ideas proposed by the participants also consists in encouraging all kinds of comments and even jokes. "Didactic game" serves as an important pedagogical tool for activating the teaching process in the educational environment of HEIs. In the course of the didactic game, the student should perform work/actions/movements similar to the work/actions/movements that may occur in his professional activity. As a result, accumulation of knowledge, updating and turning them into skills, accumulation of personal experience and its development takes place. Didactic game technology consists of three stages. Involvement in a didactic game, playful development of professional activity according to its model helps the systematic and holistic development of the profession. Internship with the performance of a position/official role is an active teaching method of teaching, in which the field of professional activity, reality itself as a "model", and imitation mainly implies the performance of a role (position). The main condition of the internship is to perform certain actions/work/activities under the supervision of a teacher in real production conditions. "Imitation training" (imitation training) refers to training and polishing certain professional skills and competencies for working with various technical tools and devices. The situation/situation and environment of the professional activity is simulated and the technical means (trainers, measuring equipment, etc.) itself serves as a "model". "Game-based design" is a practical activity during which engineering, construction, technological, social and other types of projects are developed in a game environment that reproduces the reality/real situation as much as possible. This method is characterized by a high degree of convergence/combination of individual and joint work of students. Creating a joint/common project for a group requires, on the one hand, knowledge of the technology of the design process, and on the other hand, the ability to communicate and maintain/maintain interpersonal relationships for professional problem-solving. "Computer technologies of education" are the processes of collecting, processing, storing and transmitting information to the student through a computer. Today, such technological trends are developing. In it, the computer performs the following tasks: • means of providing educational material to students for the purpose of knowledge transfer; • a means of providing information to educational processes as an additional source of information/information; • a means of determining the level of knowledge and controlling the assimilation of educational material; • a universal simulator for developing the skills of practical application of knowledge; • means of conducting educational experiments and business games on the subject of study; • one of the

most important elements in the future professional activity of the student.

Interactive forms of education play a special role in the teaching of humanities, which in turn has a system-forming effect on the formation of general cultural competences of students. The role of the subjects of the block of humanitarian sciences in the formation of UMK is conditioned by their contribution/help to:

- development of students' creative activity;
- formation of personal readiness to apply knowledge and skills;
- development of communicative and organizational skills;
- formation of universal (humanistic) values;
- expansion of environmental consciousness;
- mastering knowledge of psychology, pedagogical psychology;
- the ability to receive continuous education throughout life and re-learn when necessary, etc.

Prospective forms of teaching humanities and natural sciences cycle subjects in the formation of universal competences: seminars, creative discussions/debates, formation of pedagogical culture, dialogue, conflict situations, pedagogical deformations, consultation/advice on modern pedagogical technologies, tasks for developing students' design-research culture skills and others, and students and teachers interact during them. One of the means of forming general cultural competences in an innovative educational environment is the use of modular teaching technologies that allow for the unity of general and special practical training, which helps to implement the formation of general cultural competences. In the course of modular training, communicative culture develops, activity in cognitive activities, competence in reflexive assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities; the ability to independently manage one's own professional activities, etc. Organization of the socio-educational environment of higher educational institution through the development of students' self-management system, participation of students in public/social organizations, sports and creative clubs, students' scientific societies is also an important condition for the formation of general cultural competences of students. In this case, at each age stage, the student's social activity, social obligations/scope/quantity of responsibility and the student should grow according to the experience he receives. Social activity serves/acts as a motivating need for activity (dolzarb need), as a characteristic of a person at a certain stage of his development, and as a result of socially valuable activity. The need for social activity is implemented in the system of value goals/goals/orientations, which determine the purposeful institutions, motivational field of the person, orientation of his interests/interests and selection of appropriate methods of activity. An indicator of the formation of social activity at a certain stage of its development is a change in motivation/motivation, directing this motivation to satisfy the need for socially significant activities and socially valuable communication. In general, the components of social activity can be expressed as four domains: personality traits/characteristics, interpersonal interactions, motivation/motivation, and self-actualization. Student self-management (independent) is one of the forms of social work, which represents initiative, independent social activity of students, is aimed at solving important issues of students' life, supporting their social activity, social initiatives. One of these initiatives is community work to help first-year students adapt to training sessions, they help to form students' social activity, to quickly find their own way (solution) in difficult situations, to be independent in a new team, and to develop initiative. , helps to form the skills of independent decision-making, the ability to defend one's opinions, etc. Student self-management as a component of an innovative educational environment aims to include as many students as

possible in the organization of the educational process based on the integration/combination of pedagogical management and student self-management efforts, which means that learning/teaching/educational work allows to increase efficiency. Modeling self-management of students, identifying a set of pedagogical conditions that help to optimize the educational process, including the formation of general cultural competences of undergraduates: the democratic nature of relations, the approach to self-management as an integral self-developing system, the content of student self-management from the formation of professional competencies, management of the goal and the existence of a common purpose of self-management subsystems, coordination of actions/works for the implementation of collective activities, transfer of responsibilities and powers to others, cooperation of faculty and student groups, pedagogical management taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students, sorting of assets/activities it allows to develop on the basis of a scientifically based model, which is considered to form a positive orientation of the work of student organizations. When talking about the technologies of education/teaching in an innovative educational environment that form the general cultural competence of bachelor students, it should be noted that the socio-economic changes in the society of Uzbekistan, the activation (activation) of international relations, the transformation of the industrial society into an information society, the national consciousness of individual social groups and all peoples. development, - the change in the role of people in this system of relations increases the need for a highly cultured mobile specialist in society. In such conditions, priority issues (goals, directions) change, a new ideal of a student with general cultural competences appears. The general cultural competences are the active life activities of a person, his ability to find his way in various spheres of social and professional life, to harmonize the inner world and relationships with the surrounding world, and one of the main characteristics/virtues that a student should acquire is to independently and proactively find solutions to various problems. determines the ability.

REFERENCES

1. The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". Decree No. PD-60 of January 28, 2022. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>
2. Decree No. PD-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan"
3. Байденко, В.И. Компетенции в профессиональном образовании (к освоению компетентностного подхода) / В.Байденко // Высшее образование в России. - 2004. - №11- С.
4. Белкин, Е. Л. Дидактические проблемы управления учебно-познавательной деятельностью / Е. Л. Белкин, У. К. Карпов, П. И. Харнаш. — Ярославль: Б. и., 2020. — 175 с.
5. Беспалько, В. П. Педагогика и прогрессивные технологии обучения [Текст] / В. П. Беспалько – М.: Изд-во Педагогика, 1995. – С. 60-72. 30.
6. Борлакова З.А. Формирование общекультурных компетенций будущих бакалавров в образовательной среде вуза // Образование. Наука. Инновации. Южное измерение. Научно - образовательный журнал. №1 (27). - Ростов-на- Дону: ЮФУ, 2013. – С. 101-108.

7. Гафурова Н. В. Инновационный подход к подготовке преподавателей для системы профессионального образования / Н. В. Гафурова, С. И. Осипова // Высш. образование сегодня. - 2009. - № 6. - С. 72-75.
8. Зимняя И.А. Ключевые компетентности как результативно-целевая основа компетентностного подхода в образовании. Авторская версия. - М: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2004.
9. Киргуева Ф.Х. Компетенции как фактор деятельности существования учителя в условиях модернизации образования. - // Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. – Выпуск 1, Майкоп: 2009. - С. 61-67.
10. Muslimov N.A., Usmonboeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Toraev A.B. Basics of pedagogical competence and creativity / Study guide - Tashkent, 2015. - 120 pages.